

“Implementation of digital public relations in government in indonesia and thailand”

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Abstract

Government Public Relations utilizes Digital Public Relations (PR) communication media to be able to convey Government policies, so they are required to comprehensively understand all the functions and duties of PR as the front guard in maintaining the "face of the organization" in digital media and the performance and ability of PR to utilize digital media as best as possible. The research carried out aims to: To find the implementation, To find obstacles and To find out what efforts of Government Digital Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand, The research method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection through interviews, observation and documentation with the informant selection technique using purposive sampling of 7 (seven) informants. The results of the research show that: 1. Implementation of Digital Public Relations in Indonesia and in Thailand, the transparency conveyed must be correct and supported by factual data and still conform to the rules of Public Information Openness obtained through Digital Public Relations media in Indonesia via Instagram, FaceBook , Tiktok, Twitter, or Website. Information in Thailand was obtained through Instagram, Line, Facebook and Television as well as several bloggers and vloggers. There is information segmentation as a communication

technician and facilitator in the Indonesian Government with information packaging as well. If there is a discrepancy, make a press release, press conference and maximize the dissemination of information. The benefits obtained include a lot of support or input from outside, a positive image of the Government. The proliferation of blog posts that reinterpret content from other sources affects social systems. 2. Obstacles to the implementation of Government Digital Public Relations, if the implementation is not correct, it will reduce the success of government programs, the quality of public services and the lack of use of information in the decision making process and sometimes requires more updates and the need to find out something new and how to convey some information takes time with limited human resources, facilities and infrastructure. 3. Efforts to implement Digital Public Relations by providing regulations that support the implementation of Digital Public Relations, there must be good coordination and training for HR needs to be provided, providing effective news and information and connecting directly with the community and stakeholders in real time. The government also motivates people to carry out reforms.

Keywords: Implementation, Digital, Public Relations, Government

1.1. Background

Government public relations has a very large role in the tactical (short term) government administration system, trying to provide effective messages and information to motivate and have a very big influence on society through the messages it conveys. Long-term message (strategic role) Government Public Relations plays an active role in the decision-making process, in providing brilliant suggestions, ideas and creative ideas to implement the program of the institution concerned. (Ruslan, 2011)

In general, the objectives of Government Public Relations involve three things, namely: a) Reputation and image. Public relations duties cannot be separated from reputation and image, meaning the assumption that a positive image will be related to high public access to the output of the organization; b) Communication bridge, Public Relations becomes a communicator and mediator in conveying aspirations to the government; c) Mutual benefit relationship, public relations must guarantee that the government is in its operations, has good intentions in realizing social responsibility and is expressed through a mutually beneficial relationship between the government and the public (Nilasari, 2012)

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has fundamentally changed human civilization, with the introduction of digitalization which refers to a situation describing changes in lifestyle and behavior of individuals and organizations. This development of course requires an appropriate response from various parties, including Government Public Relations, utilizing Digital Public Relations (PR) communication media.) is an important thing to do in conveying policies, so digital public relations is needed which focuses more on online platforms and social media to reach the public through virtual spaces. (Hasbiran, 2018)

Based on the statement (Gabrina & Suharyanti, 2017) that in order to achieve success in practicing Public Relations online, there are four basic elements of online Public Relations that PR practitioners must pay attention to, namely transparency, porosity, the internet as an agent, richness in content, and reach. So the author assumes that cyber public relations can be said to be effective if it fulfills these four elements.

There has been a lot of related research that utilizes digital public relations in socializing government programs, such as in research conducted by (Margaretha & Sunarya, 2017) regarding Instagram as a Socialization Media with nine superior Government programs, it was found that Instagram has the potential to be used as a socialization media because it has features- features that meet the seven aspects of credibility, context, content, clarity, continuity and consistency, channels and capability of the audience. as well as managing the flagship program of the Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises of the Republic of Indonesia which can run according to plan.

To optimize the digital function of PR, the following are PR activities that can be carried out digitally, namely by carrying out digital PR activities, PR practitioners are required to comprehensively understand all the functions and tasks of PR as the front guard in maintaining the "face of the organization" in the digital media they manage by (Nurjanah & Nurnisya, 2016) regarding the use of Digital Public Relations (PR) in the socialization of the Yogyakarta City Government Public Relations tagline "Jogja special", research findings show that the use of Digital Public Relations in the socialization of "Jogja special" has not been effective due to the process of introducing and campaigning. through interaction by utilizing resources, facilities and infrastructure that have not yet touched on the goals and objectives of socialization, namely gaining identity, developing the noble values contained in the branding "special Jogja.

(Gabrina & Suharyanti, 2017) also explains about reach in Cyber PR. Reach or public reach for content can be created in various ways. Companies can use several techniques so that company website pages can be easily found by the public, such as search engine optimization

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

and hyperlink exchange. Apart from that, reach can also be achieved through online community involvement which makes people closer to the company, so that the company also becomes part of the community conversations that are formed online.

As previously explained, effectiveness is a measurement of the achievement of predetermined goals or objectives. Based on the statement (Phillips dan Young (2009: 45), 2009) that in order to achieve success in carrying out online Public Relations practices, there are four basic elements of online Public Relations that PR practitioners must pay attention to, namely transparency, porosity, the internet as an agent, richness in content, and reach. So the author assumes that cyber public relations can be said to be effective if it fulfills these four elements, so that it can facilitate interaction and speed the dissemination of information which causes public opinion to spread to all levels of society with various opinions. Social media-based reputation management is likened to a double-edged sword in managing public opinion. The more positive the opinion formed, the better the image and reputation of the organization. Conversely, the more negative public opinion, the worse the image and reputation. (Pratama & Safrianti, 2017), so not everyone can experience a positive reputation, because this is also influenced by the performance and ability of PR practitioners to make the best use of digital media. The research conducted was analyzed using theory from (Phillips dan Young (2009: 45), 2009) regarding the four basic elements of online public relations that PR practitioners must pay attention to, so that from this research a digital PR practice that is appropriate and measurable can be produced from the perspective of view theory as well as existing reality, thereby contributing to the development of science and technology as well as the discovery of new theories and concepts or models. Formulation of the problem, based on the background of the problem, the research objectives are as follows: 1. How is the implementation of Digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand?; 2. What are the obstacles to implementing Digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand?; 3. What are the efforts to implement Digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand?

Research methods

The research method that will be used in: Implementation of Digital Public Relations for Government in Indonesia and Thailand, by collaborating with Foreign Lecturers, namely from the Thai Global Business Administration Technological College, Thailand. The research team conducted this research to determine the mapping regarding the implementation of digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand so as to obtain a model for implementing digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand with the obstacles and efforts made by Public Relations in managing digital PR. The research method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection through interviews, observation and documentation. The informant selection technique used purposive sampling of 8 (eight) informants consisting of Public Relations and TIM, as well as the people of both countries for discussions both online and offline.

In this research, data collection techniques are through interviews and observations with the parameters of transparency, porosity, the internet as an agent, richness in content, and reach, as well as inhibiting factors and efforts made by Public Relations, so the author assumes that digital public relations can be said to be effective if these four elements are met, and with the presence of data analysis techniques, the results of the analysis data that will be calculated will be valid.

Research result

1. Implementation of Digital Government Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

Thus, the information contained in Government Digital Public Relations both in Indonesia and Thailand is transparent in conveying development according to the main tasks and functions, and the information conveyed about regional government activities which include development, activity budgets, regional leadership activities, and open regional developments. and accepted by everyone.

Packaging of Government Digital Public Relations messages, segmentation or specific targets of Government Digital Public Relations according to informants can be segmented as follows:

Field of Work Information	Digital Public Relations Segmentation Government	Information
Civil Servants outside Java*	None	The target audience is considered the same so there is no need for segmentation
Public Relations Outside Java* Yes	Yes	
Human Resource Management (Thailand)*	Yes	Citizen in general
Head of Department*	Yes	There are people who know the activities of the Cirebon City Regional Government, especially the people of Cirebon City
Creative Regency Government*	Yes	exists to build and develop a positive image of Cirebon Regency
Lecture (Thailand)*		I think I dont get any target but some segment is to develop society 5.0
Student (Thailand)*		I think there are some target but I have no ideas

Information: *Informant profile data is with the researcher

Government Digital Public Relations requires segmentation in the hope of conveying information to the public in accordance with the expectations and duties of Public Relations as communication technicians and facilitators in the Government. Meanwhile, one of the Regional Government Civil Servants said there was none because the target audience was the same.

The strategy for disseminating information in governments outside Java is carried out through the media which includes activities and is also conveyed to Instagram and Facebook, while in Thailand news releases are obtained via TV and even Line as well as the Thai people's concern for social media and technology and the government always provides updates in the application. or website to be announced to the public and they get it from several bloggers and vloggers. In the Cirebon City Government, it starts with identifying and analyzing issues that exist in the Cirebon City area, collecting data and information related to these issues, implementing issues related to existing policies in the Cirebon City Regional Government, analyzing the scale of impact and the scale of possibility to determine the scale of risk, publishing information to various platforms and media, evaluating the results of information dissemination and publication through media, both digital and print.

Table 1. Information Dissemination Strategy

Field of Work Information	Dissemination strategy	Description
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IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

Civil Servants outside Java*	Via Media	
Public Relations Outside Java* Yes	IG and Facebook	
Human Resource Management (Thailand)*	TV and Social Media. such as FB, Instagram, Line	News release
Head of Department*	yes	Identifying and analyzing issues in the Cirebon City area, Collecting data and information related to these issues, Implementing issues related to existing policies in the Cirebon City Regional Government, Analyzing the scale of impact and the scale of possibility to determine the scale of risk, Publishing information to various platforms and media , evaluate the results of information dissemination
Creative Regency Government*	Through media, both digital and print	
Lecture (Thailand)*	blogger and vlogger	sending the information
Student (Thailand)*	social media and technology and government	always give update in the application or website to announce to society”

Information: *Informant profile data is with the researcher

They provide several websites and social media to deliver information to society

Figure 1.1. Cirebon City Government Instagram in Indonesia
Source: Informant

Available on Government/Institution Social Media, very good and accurate, Broadcast

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

on TV and radio network and internet, In accordance with the rules on Openness of Public Information in (1) Law on Openness of Public Information No. 14 of 2008 Chapter IV concerning Information that Must be Provided and Announced and (2) Cirebon City Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2022 concerning the Implementation of Communication and Informatics, Statistics and Coding in Paragraph 2 concerning Public Information Management and Services, the information is very accurate because the news source is stated The information is open. They provide several websites and social media to deliver information to society

Informant 7 said the following:

"They do some partnerships and make massive promotions"

Figure 1.2. Government Website in Thailand

Source: Informant

The government encourages or interprets information which generally includes advertising in cyberspace or similar promotions by providing the widest possible opportunity to utilize the media it has with information conveyed only in the form of "Government spokesperson", information conveyed in accordance with the target audience, preparing materials attractive copywriting, and choosing the right media for conveying information, as well as providing the widest possible opportunity to utilize the media they have. The government also supports every detail of the information and conveys the truth, they form partnerships and carry out massive promotions. (Nurfalah et al., 2020) experienced, then constructing the entire explanation of the meaning and essence of the experience. The results of the study found that young Instagram users have a clear stance, goals and desires, they actively construct themselves as a student identity including displays, reality and agents on social media in the form of photo posts, videos, status updates and instances, as well as giving emojis and giving each other comments. The self-commitment to identity is accepted as a reinforcement of their identity and becomes their self-concept. Users are also recognized for their identity in organizations, the hobby community, and academics. The Students' self-identity models in Instagram social media that occur by being introduced and reinforced by their self-concept and it is expected that the function of social media is used for positive things related to the development of student identity as late teens and as the nation's successor who has a firm stand with high integrity and can avoid a high "narcissistic" culture which can also be a reference for students. at other universities.

Efforts to get interaction with external parties through social media with transparency regarding public information, there must be collaboration with third parties. Informants prefer easy ways to get information on social media and try to provide interactive information and answer questions in accordance with existing government policies, they even stay in touch with the community and several parties, they also approach and discuss interaction with external

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

parties and transparency of public information.

The benefits obtained from various types of information regarding government are disseminated in the form of Community Services, Relations between the Government, Community and Business Actors, Community Empowerment through information, more efficient Government Implementation, getting lots of support or input from outside, "To ensure that we have the rights and eligibility to gain access to certain benefits, a positive image of the Regional Government of Cirebon City, Government policies can be known to the public, and the public can find out about the activities carried out by the leadership and Regional Government of Cirebon City, the Community and the public can learn more and get information easily, the Community can find out information quickly, Community Services, Relations between Government, Community and Business Actors, Community Empowerment through information, more efficient Government Implementation

The way to convey information is either informal or more transparent. The information conveyed must be correct and supported by factual data. The information conveyed verbally wherever and has been planned. More transparent. The way to convey information either informally or more transparently still conforms to the rules on Openness of Public Information. contained in (1) Public Information Openness Law no. 14 of 2008 Chapter IV concerning Information that Must be Provided and Announced and (2) Cirebon City Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2022 concerning the Implementation of Communication and Informatics, Statistics and Coding in Paragraph 2 concerning Public Information Management and Services, social media is the best way to disseminate information, Social media is a good tool. The information conveyed must be correct and supported by factual data.

Message/information or story changing during the process through cyberspace is a normal and common phenomenon. What are the facts that show the proliferation of blog posts that reinterpret content from other sources, which are also called human internet agencies.

The proliferation of blocks is due to the large number of writers who convey ideas and all thoughts in written form," "The phenomenon of changes in information through cyberspace is now a normal and common phenomenon where social relations or as changes to the balance of social relations and all forms of changes in institutions social institutions in a society. This influences the social system, including values, attitudes and behavioral patterns among groups in society. The fact of the proliferation of posts is also because the information has a social relationship with readers, the information conveyed is becoming a public issue, and the information conveyed is unique in language style and it is best that the information must be sourced from the institution that issued the information, because the information is conveyed by other parties. it may not be up to date and, sometimes people want to comment and suggest ways to develop it, for example sometimes they are not satisfied with government policies so they write on blogs.

The government's collaboration with third parties in providing information online has varied answers, some say never, others say yes. The government collaborates with various local, regional and national media in disseminating information both online and offline. The government is very active in creating something new and updating to convey more useful information.

There are company website pages in cyberspace that give their own impression about the government, some say yes, some say no, for various reasons. Informants such as through online someone can easily get information. The amount of online information provided both by the government itself, a number of other people, and internet technology and contributors (agents). Following are the results of the interview:

Informant 7 said the following:

“Very good, because it will make it easier to find the necessary data”

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

Figure 1.3. Manpawah City Government Website in Indonesia
Source: Informant

The amount of online information provided both by the government itself, a number of other people, and internet technology and contributors (agents) is very good, because it will make it easier to find the necessary data, the government can provide the creation of a website so that the public can access information about regional data, Some from the government but more from other agents, the more information provided by the government and media/contributors online the better it will be so that people can get to know local governments more closely, have more information but it is updated every day, the information is very large and I didn't get the detailed numbers, which is very good, because it will make it easier to find the necessary data.

2. Obstacles in implementing Digital Government Public Relations

Obstacles in implementing Digital Public Relations in Government based on interview results are as follows:

Informant 4 said the following:

"If implementation is not correct it will reduce the success of the government program. "This certainly has an adverse effect on the quality of public services and the lack of use of information in the decision-making process by involving the community in it."

Informant 7 said the following:

"Limitations of Human Resources, Facilities and Infrastructure, Limited Human Resources, Facilities and Infrastructure, lack of coordination from institutions, insufficient HR competency, Instability of Internet network"

If implementation is not correct it will reduce the success of the government program. This certainly has an adverse effect on the quality of public services and the lack of use of information in the decision-making process by involving the community in it. sometimes it takes more updates and needs to figure out something new and how to convey some

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

information and it takes time. Maybe how to share information that is good and not fake. Limited human resources, facilities and infrastructure

3. Efforts to implement Digital Public Relations

Efforts to implement Digital Public Relations are as follows:

Informant 4 said the following:

“Providing effective news and information so that it can have an influence on society through the news and information conveyed. "Apart from that, you can connect directly with the community and stakeholders in real time."

Informant 7 said the following:

"Provide rules that support the implementation of Digital Public Relations"

Providing rules that support the implementation of Digital Public Relations, there must be good coordination and training for HR needs to be provided. There is not much that needs to be mentioned about this. Providing effective news and information so that it can have an influence on society through the news and information conveyed. Apart from that, the community and stakeholders can be connected directly in real time. The government motivates the community to make updates. They make more efforts to provide the best to the community, providing regulations that support the implementation of Digital Public Relations.

CONCLUSION

1. Implementation of Digital Public Relations in Indonesia and Thailand means that the transparency of the information provided by the Government in Thailand and Indonesia must be correct and supported by factual data and still conform to the rules of Public Information Openness in conveying development. This information was obtained through Government Digital Public Relations media in Indonesia via Instagram, FaceBook, Tiktok, Twitter and the Website. Information in Thailand was obtained through Instagram, Line, Facebook and Television as well as several bloggers and vloggers. There is segmentation of information to the public in accordance with the expectations and duties of Public Relations as communication technicians and facilitators in the Indonesian Government with information packaging starting from identifying and analyzing issues, collecting data, implementing issues related to policy, analyzing the scale of impact and the scale of possibility to determine the scale of risk, then publish the information to various platforms and media, as well as evaluate the results of information dissemination for publication through media, both digital and print. The Thai government provides the widest opportunity to utilize the media it has in the form of "Government spokesperson", conveying information according to the target audience, preparing copywriting material, and choosing the right media. The government also supports every detail of the information and conveys the truth. If there is a discrepancy, respond to the dissemination of information by making press releases, press conferences and maximizing the dissemination of factual and hoax information so that the public is protected from hoax news/information and can find out information wisely. Information from Government Institutions and Digital Public Relations does not serve advertisements that are not to promote the area, and the public will abandon access to fake news, whether international news or word of mouth, not from official channels and collaboration with third parties. The benefits obtained from various types of

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL PUBLIC RELATIONS IN GOVERNMENT IN INDONESIA AND THAILAND

information on government implementation are more efficient, as well as getting a lot of support or input from outside, a positive image of the Government, Government policies can be known to the public, and the public can find out about the activities carried out by the leadership and the Government and can learn more and get information by easy. The proliferation of blog posts that reinterpret content from other sources, which are also called human internet agencies. This influences the social system including the values, attitudes and behavioral patterns of society. The government collaborates with third parties in providing information with various local, regional and national media in disseminating information both online and offline which is very good, because it makes it easier to find the necessary data.

2. Obstacles to implementing Digital Government Public Relations, if implementation is not correct, it will reduce the success of government programs. This certainly has an adverse effect on the quality of public services and the lack of use of information in the decision making process and sometimes requires more updates and the need to find out something new and how to convey some information requires time with limited human resources, facilities and infrastructure.
3. Efforts to implement Digital Public Relations by providing regulations that support the implementation of Digital Public Relations, there must be good coordination and training for HR needs to be provided, providing effective news and information so that they can have an influence on society through the news and information conveyed. Apart from that, you can connect directly with the community and stakeholders in real time. The government also motivates people to carry out reforms. Daftar Pustaka

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